

Experimental method for determining the atomistic details of the Quantum well interface

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Introduction

The concentration and mobility of electrons, and the valley splitting (VS) of the 6-fold-degenerate conduction band of bulk silicon are important considerations for realizing robust spin qubits in gate-defined quantum dots (QDs) fabricated in Si/SiGe quantum wells (QWs).

Here we report the carrier density and mobility in sub-surface Si/SiGe QWs, and attempt to estimate the VS, by measurement of (temperature-dependent) Shubnikov DeHaas oscillations. Anomalies in the quantum Hall data are also discussed

Si/SiGe heterostructure, Hall-bar design and fabrication

Schematic of the Si/SiGe HEMT structure CAD Design of the Hall bar Microscope image of the Hall bar

- The Si QW is 30 nm below the surface.
- Ohmic contacts are created by a combination of photolithography, phosphorus ion-implantation, post-implantation annealing and Ti/Au deposition, by electron beam evaporation.
- An 80-nm chemical-vapor-deposition-(CVD)-grown SiO₂ separates the ohmic contacts from the surface gate for carrier accumulation, patterned in the Hall bar geometry.
- Accumulation gate leakage current is found to be 60 pA at 6V.

Measurement of Hall bars on Si/SiGe QWs: Quantum Hall Effect (QHE) & Shubnikov de Haas (SdH) data

TLM measurement

SdH oscillations

Valley splitting from SdH data

SdH oscillations

Thermal activation measurements of valley splitting

Ongoing work and future outlook

Understanding the anomalous Hall data

Intermixed R_{XX} & R_{XY} can arise due to (a) potential disorder along the length of the Hall bar, (b) a parallel classical conductance channel, and/or (c) angled arms of the accumulation gate may also cause intermixing.

Simulation Results

R_{xx} and R_{xy} (Straight arms)

R_{xx} and R_{xy} (Angled arms, 45°)

Potential profile

Modified potential profile as compared to standard Hall bar to include short (hetero interface) and long (oxide interface) range scattering.

Fabrication of Si/SiGe QDs, to host spin qubits

SEM image of a 2x2 quantum dot array on an identical heterostructure.

Three fine gate layers allow confinement, accumulation and depletion of electrons.

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